

Millenial Politeness in Whats'app Application Communication

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ABSTRACT: The technology development change the traditional become the digital. In this digital era, communication take place not only sit side by side, but the presence of smartphone make the distance meaningless. The change from the traditional into digital shift the great value in Indonesia , politeness, especially for millenial generation in STIE Bina Karya. This study is going to see millenial generation communication with their lecturers through WA communication tool. The data were taken by documentation and interview some lecturers who have received the WA text from the millenial generation which belong to impoliteness from Januari 2020 until January 2021. Millenial generation who love the hedonism and freedom, can not away from their gadget and the internet. As the result, they prove the impoliteness in WA text when they texting their lecturers, they create the impolite word choice which made the situation become unfriendly, they give impulse to the lecturer and also they give no option in dedicing a decision meanwhile lecturer/institution has made the regulation for running the learning system.

KEYWORDS: politeness, Millenial Genaration, Whatsapp text

I. INTRODUCTION

Globalization and technology are two unseparatable thing which give impact for all human activities (Tawadrous et al., 2016) including in communication system. The presence of technology made the communication process become faster, efficient, personally and at the right person (Nuswantoro, 2015). Communication happened in human life. It can be in form of verbal communication and non verbal communication (Khotimah, 2019) in order to deliver information about his/her ideas, thought and decision (Bahri, 2018). Verbal communication is delivering information by words, spoken or written and can be through listening and reading (Wahyuni, 2018). Whereas non verbal communication is delivering information without words but through gesture, eye contact, face expression, sounds, touch and dressing (Puspita, 2015). In this research, the reseachers are going to focus on verbal communication.

The presence of technology nowadays give several easiness for people in communication system. For example people utilize smartphones in order to facilitate them to communicate with those whom stay in a distance in form of text messages or a call (Kubackova, 2015). People in all age do this verbal communication in their family, education, business and work through their smartphones (National Institute of Agricultural Extension Management, 2000), including the Millenial Generation or digital generation or Gen Y. They utilize their smartphone including the internet as the source of worldwide information as their daily needs (Sari et al., 2020). Those who belong to Millenial Generation was born in the year 1980 through 2000 (Hidayatullah et al., 2018) (Christ Dass et al., 2021), along with the emergence of new technology for instance laptop, handphone, social meda like Facebook, Twitter, MySpace and Blogger. The Millenial generation who now between 15 years old – 34 years old, they have a specific characteristics. For instance, technological savvy, cultural acceptance, flexibility and multitasking, being independent and prefer working together (Islam et al., 2011). However, Millenial Generation have the less concern to their social circumtances, they prefer to freedom and hedonism, optimalizing their own happiness and pleasure (Hariyati, 2017). This situation is contradict with western culture. Even so, as a social beings we have to adhere the great value in our social life like characteristics that become a life pattern (Salim, 2016).

The use of mobile phones in several decades are getting advanced due to users' mobility and convenience(Tawadrous et al., 2016). Now people are familiar with the name smartphone, although the basic function is the same. Smartphones are provided with modern technology, especially for communication such as voice and text communication (Jones et al., 2011) which users can download several applications like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Path, Line and WhatsApp (WA)(Puspita, 2015). This research

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focus on the use of WhatsApp application. WA serves its users for text, photos distribution, videos and voice notes among the smartphone users (Thota & Divatia, 2015).

According to Aisyah and Hardika (2018) the development of sophisticated devices changes the paradigm of politeness from past to present like in dressing, communicating, and manner behaving. We can not avoid the degradation politeness when modernity covers the social environment. Ethics is the main key in social environment acceptance toward somebody. Thus, etiquette or ethics lead us having a good relation between human or rules or having a good behavior in relationship with others (Nur Aisyah & Hardika, 2019). They added, politeness can be felt as a good behaviour, having manners or social etiquette, having a good social behaviour, and having a positive thinking. Therefore, making politeness as the habitual repetition in building a good social environment is a good decision.

According to Lakoff (quoted by Anggraini et al, 2019) there are three terms to decide whether the utterances are polite or impolite: 1) Do not impose, 2) Give options, and 3) Make a feel good to be friendly (Anggraini et al., 2019).

In STIE Bina Karya, the implementation of WA communication is accepted, among lecturers, between college students, and between lecturers and college students when they can not see each other. Usually they will discuss related to their course needs. Most of the college students are millennial generation only less are not. Even, some of the lecturer are Millennial Generation too. Since this research is going to see the millennial politeness in WhatsApp communication between students and lecturer, the researchers choose STIE Bina Karya as the place for conducting this research. STIE Bina Karya is one of institutes North Sumatra, Indonesia, which is suitable for gaining the data from STIE Bina Karya's students who belong to millennial generation.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive qualitative research which apply the postpositivism approach which aims is to observe the research object's condition naturally and the researchers were as the main instrument because the researchers make the conclusion based on the researchers' interview and other supporting data. Qualitative research is utilized for observing the human life, a history, behaviour and social activity. Therefore this method is trying to find out and understand what was hidden behind the phenomena which is difficult to fully comprehended (Moha & sudrajat, 2019).

The researchers gained the data by collecting the WA text from the college students who belongs to Millennial Generation among 17-33 taken from STIE Bina Karya's lecturers. As the technique data collection, the researchers applied data triangulation. The result of qualitative research was emphasized on the meaning then generalization (Puspita, 2015). This research describe how millennial generation's politeness in having WA text communication with their lecturer in their study. For the data triangulation, the researchers interviewed other lecturers who ever experienced accepting the WA text from the college students who belong to millennial generation. The purpose of the interview was to emphasize the collected data from the observation and documentation, whether it is appropriate or not, if it is not, there will be further observation. The researchers kept about the informans' identity without write them down in this research. This research took place in STIE Bina Karya. Since not all the college students belong to Millennial generation, the researchers only focus on the WA texts which were sent by college students who belong to millennial generation. This researchers took the data from January 2020 until January 2021.

III. DISCUSSION

WA is introduced as communication tool to help users to have communication with whom they want to talk to, personally or in work team not only that the presence of WA can help users in complex decision making assignments (Urien et al., 2019). In WA, everyone can send text or voice note to their family, friends, work team, teachers, lecturers and so on when they are far away. Even so, whoever he is, he has to adhere the norm of politeness in language which applies in Indonesia. It is not only about word choice, but also the way the speaker deliver the messages. For instance, the good word choice do not guarantee that the speaker is polite, however it categorize as impolite when the way he delivers his words is in a bad manner. Furthermore, in our social life there is a social hierarchy which determine a certain appraisal among people like between parents and children, employer and employee, teacher and student, the rich and the poor and other status (Çelik et al., 2018). When the way of delivering his word does not appropriate with the available cultural norms in Indonesia, the bad stereotipe will stick on himself as an arrogant, indifferent, selfish, and uncivilized person. Picture 1 displays how impolite word choice of a college student texting his lecture.

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Lecturer: *It is up to you if you want to do the remedial test. The fact is You were absent on the date of the test.*

Student: *Ok, Fine, Sir. Sometimes I do not understand with lecturer's character. I am wrong when I send the information, and if there is no news, I am wrong too. The fact is students always wrong in lecturers' sight and lecturer always right. Ok, thank you for your lesson. I will try your suggestion.*

Picture 1. The Impolite Word Choice to be Unfriendly

Picture 1 is a text from a male seventh semester student. He sent this text in the middle of Mid term test because he was late one day to submit his answer sheet from the schedule. He wanted to inform the lecturer the reason of his lateness, he wanted to bargain about submitting his answer sheet. Meanwhile, college students have to submit their answer sheet at the time that already scheduled, if not, they will have the complementary test and it is not free. Since this is a formal institution, everyone have to obey the regulation, including on the answer sheet submission. Not only that, deservedly, students respect their lecturers who give them a lesson (Fatriani, 2015). From picture 1, it shows the unpoliteness through the word choice by the students. It seems like he sent the text to his mate, the fact is it is for his lecturer. It was his fault for being late in the mid term test submission. He did not agree the lecturer's answer for not accepting his answer sheet. Previously, it was clear enough written in the announcement that there is no excuse for late submission.

In picture 2, the millennial generation shows the impoliteness through the WA text by imposing the lecturer.

Good Morning, Miss. I am so sorry for disturbing your weekend. Where are you, Miss. May I have your time? I want to get your signature for my thesis proposal. I want to register for the SPSS. Help me please, Miss. I really really need your help. Yesterday, my sister was late to see you. That was my fault.

Picture 2. The imposing WA text

In picture 2, the student has a good word choice but the way she deliver her text was impolite. She was imposing the lecturer. In this situation, the eight semester female student was in the injury time for finishing her thesis proposal. She contacted her advisor

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three days before the registration deadline for having the SPSS. College students have SPSS (Statistical Product and Service Solutions) after finishing the chapter 1 until 3 of their thesis and got signature from their advisor means they may continue to chapter 4 to 5 and take the SPSS. Since she is working out of the city, she has no time for consulting her proposal to her advisor. She said that she worked for continuing her study. Whatever the reason, she must have the priority for her life, what should be the first at the close time. She knows her responsibility as a college student and she knows her responsibility as an employee. The institution has given a year for college students to finish their thesis. The decision is on her (Samekto et al., 2014). And now, it is the close time for them to finish their thesis, meanwhile her chapter 1 – 3 has not accepted yet by the advisor. In this WA text she wanted the signature of the advisor, though the advisor rejected it.

Next, picture 3 displays the impoliteness by not giving an option to the lecturer as his/her thesis advisor. As a social being, people have to keep the harmony between speaker and receiver while having communication (Alfiat, 2015).

Assalamualaikum, Good morning, Mam, how are you? I hope you are fine. Amin. I apologize, I am XXXX from YYYY class who take marketing management as my major. I want to tell you related to thesis consultation because I am from YYYY class which at Monday to Friday I work, so I beg you how if the thesis consultation held every Friday, Mam. Once again, I am really sorry for my words, Mam.

Picture 3. Giving No Option WA text

In his study, he said that the purpose of delivering an idea is to exchange thought between speaker and receiver, not to insult anyone (Patiung, 2016). As seen on picture 3, the student text her advisor for having the thesis consultation every Friday, whereas her thesis advisor has chosen the days for having the thesis consultation, twice a week because she is in the progress of finishing her doctoral degree. It would be better if the college student did not limit her time for seeing her thesis advisor only on Friday. However, her thesis advisor has another responsible to do in finishing her dissertation. If she can finish her thesis proposal faster, she can return to her work. The importance is they can finish their study as soon as they can and return to their responsibility at work without ignoring one of them.

IV. CONCLUSION

From the research result, it found that the millennial generation in this research tend to be impolite in texting their lecturers through WA text, the word choice they made was impolite and unfriendly, they impose the lecturer, and they give no option for the lecturer. The lecturers are older than them who have finished their study for longer than them. Definitely, they should respect them even through their words, manner, and they way they dress up. They fact, they did not want to obey the regulation that has made, from the institution and from the lecturer, too. Therefore, they made the offense which made themselves in a bad mark in the lecturer's mind. They want the bargaining meanwhile they are in an education institution which put the consistency and regularity first. In conclusion, before text the one who have different social status from us, we need to think and think again based

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on the word choice, no impulse, and give options for them, do not decide by one side. Therefore, the harmony in communication as social being can establish for a long time.

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